

Identification of the Factors of Entrepreneurship Education that Contribute to Student Entrepreneurship Development at the University of Venda

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Purpose - Higher education institutions in South Africa have implemented entrepreneurship courses, training programmes and competitions to promote student entrepreneurship development. Entrepreneurship education encourages individuals to start their businesses upon graduation, rather than seeking and relying on employment. However, research on the role of entrepreneurship education is limited. Hence, this study aims to identify factors of entrepreneurship education that contribute to student entrepreneurial development at the University of Venda. This study utilised a qualitative research design. The targeted population comprised University of Venda student-entrepreneurs who participate in entrepreneurship education programmes, and those who are registered for entrepreneurship courses. A convenience sampling technique was used to select 10 students and data was collected through semi-structured face-to-face and telephone interviews according to the research objectives. The collected data was analysed thematically using Atlas.ti version 8.4. The results identified some factors that include access to financial resources, entrepreneurship centre, entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, mentorship and coaching, networking opportunities, and practical experience. This study is among the first to have managed to identify the factors that contribute to student entrepreneurship development in a university.

Keywords: Contribution, development, entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship, factors

Unemployment is a common challenge for both developing and developed countries, and it has been on an upward trajectory after the COVID-19 pandemic (Shah, Amjed, & Jaboob, 2020). The Covid-19 pandemic devastated South Africa and left many people without jobs, causing, for instance, graduates from higher education institutions (HEI) to face hurdles in pursuing their desired careers (Ameliah & Jatnika, 2024). According to Iswati and Hastuti (2021), this is because employers now evaluate HEI graduates based on their value-added skills and talents, in addition to their academic qualifications. Various policies and tactics have been used globally to minimize unemployment (Shah et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship is now widely recognised as a tool to reduce unemployment since it focuses on individual self-employment and is crucial for a country's

economic development (Al-Lawati, Kohar, & Suleiman, 2021), making it one of the most popular alternative solutions to the unemployment problem (Shah, Amjed, & Jaboob, 2020). Many countries, including South Africa, however, have the problem of developing new entrepreneurs and influencing people's attitudes towards entrepreneurship, although policymakers have implemented a variety of policies and techniques to encourage entrepreneurship (Shah, Amjed, & Jaboob, 2020).

One of the strategies is to provide entrepreneurship education to enhance the level of competence and interest in the concept of entrepreneurship (Shah, Amjed, & Jaboob, 2020). Entrepreneurship education is divided into two categories - academic entrepreneurship education programmes and entrepreneurship training programmes. The training programmes are mostly practical, concentrating on building knowledge and skills in preparation for starting a business; on the other hand, academic entrepreneurship programmes are mostly theoretical focusing on the construction of knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship (Tshehla, Chodokufa, & Costa, 2020). Higher education institutions promote entrepreneurship by providing entrepreneurship courses and incubations, as well as implementing training programmes (Hassan, 2020). Entrepreneurship education and training among university students as well as the promotion of related activities, are becoming more significant in many countries, including South Africa (Sarpente, Bolzani, & Grimaldi, 2025; Lopez, Noguera, & Urbano, 2025; Ngobese & Beharry-Ramra, 2025).

Universities in most countries, as part of their curriculum, integrate entrepreneurship theoretical courses and practical programmes to shape students' entrepreneurial intentions and mindset and provide them with the necessary knowledge and skills. This is supported by Gupta, Sharma, and Rajput (2023) who alluded that the objectives of entrepreneurship education are to teach

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students to develop ideas, skills and managerial abilities, capacity for self-employment, as well as to encourage them to explore business as a career by cultivating positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Many empirical studies indicate that students who participate in entrepreneurship training programmes are more likely to start new enterprises, have higher entrepreneurial intentions, and more successful in spotting opportunities than other students (Sousa, Silva, Couto, & Bacelar-Nicolau, 2017; Mei, Lee, & Xiang, 2020; Cohen, Hsu, & Shinnar, 2021).

According to Sobh, Younis, and Keshta (2025), entrepreneurship education is crucial for building the skills and information needed by entrepreneurs to capitalise on business possibilities. Additionally, entrepreneurship education impacts students by boosting their market awareness, creativity, invention, and the capacity to acquire resources and commercial skills (Radebe & Vezi-Magigaba, 2021). Universities, currently, are playing a crucial role, not only in teaching but also in implementing numerous programmes and activities to promote entrepreneurship (Sousa et al., 2017). South Africa is making significant progress in encouraging entrepreneurship through courses and training programmes due to the high unemployment rate among graduates (Ncube & Lekhanya, 2025).

Entrepreneurship education has been focused on and deliberated upon in many studies, for instance Shah, Amjed, and Jaboob (2020), Bell and Bell (2020), Jardim, Bártolo, and Pinho (2021). Few studies, however, have been conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education, even though it is ranked highly relevant topic in many countries' policy agendas (Overwien, Jahnke, & Leker, 2024). A study by Handayati, Wulandari, and Soetjipto (2020) conducted in Indonesia investigated how entrepreneurship education influences the intentions of students, and the findings revealed that entrepreneurship education positively influences both entrepreneurial intentions and mindset; however, the effects of this programme are still not well recognised, regardless of the widespread promotion of the phenomenon (Tshehla, Chodokufa, & Costa, 2020). Lv et al. (2021), in their research focused on developing countries, however, there has been minimal attempt at empirical research on improvements in entrepreneurship education in the South African context (Mei, Lee, & Xiang, 2020). In 2020, the University of Venda developed a strategic plan for 2021-2025 to become an entrepreneurial institution, particularly capable of contributing to South Africa's aim of being an inclusive economy. The specific road to this transformation remains unarticulated due to a lack of scientific knowledge relating to the process of transformation into an entrepreneurial institution (Iwara & Kilonzi, 2022). The study of Kativhu and Netshandama (2024) also revealed that the transformation is still in the process due to the lack of a relevant guiding framework and principles. There is, hence, still a dearth of knowledge of the role of entrepreneurship education in entrepreneurship development; thus, further investigation is required. This study, therefore, sought to fill the gap, thereby improving the literature on entrepreneurship education research in South African universities. This led to the formulation of the research problem; subsequently, this study's aim is to identify the factors of entrepreneurship education that contribute to student entrepreneurship development at the University of Venda. The research question is: 'What are the factors of entrepreneurship education that contribute to student entrepreneurship development, in the University of Venda?'

Review of Literature

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is underpinned by the social cognitive theory (SCT), which emphasises the impact of social learning in shaping human behaviour (Boldureana, Lonescu, Berca, Bedrule-Grigorută, & Boldureana, 2020). Social Cognitive Theory was developed by Bandura in 1986; he postulates that learning occurs in a social context with a dynamic reciprocal interaction between the individual, environment, and behaviour. In entrepreneurship education context, SCT provides a clear framework to understand students' entrepreneurial intentions, which could be influenced by the interaction between the environmental input, personal characteristics, and behavioural outcomes (Nwosu, Obidike, Ugwu, Udeze, & Okolie, 2022). In the context of this study, the environmental input is represented by entrepreneurship education; personal factors are demonstrated by entrepreneurial mindset, self-efficacy, and creativity; and behavioural outcomes are represented by students' entrepreneurial intention (Widjojo, 2023). Observation and imitation influence cognitive factors, assisting the individual in determining whether to imitate a seen behaviour (Bayrón, 2013). According to SCT, behavioural outcomes are the results of a three-way reciprocal interplay between personal inputs as well as one's previous experience (Mohammed, Al qatalan, Ghawanneh, & Alqaadar, 2020). In the context of this study, experience could be interpreted as students' prior learning experiences throughout entrepreneurship education and training, which can influence their entrepreneurial intentions and act through increased self-efficacy. As a result, the more students participate in entrepreneurship education, the more likely they are to develop entrepreneurial self-efficacy, entrepreneurial attitude, and assess their abilities to become entrepreneurs, as well as practice and receive feedback from other established entrepreneurs (Nwosu et al., 2023). The study of Widjojo (2023) used SCT to evaluate how students with high levels of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial mindset, and entrepreneurial competencies improve their entrepreneurial intention. The results revealed that entrepreneurship education has a substantial impact on entrepreneurial competencies, intentions, and attitudes. An entrepreneurial mindset has little impact on intention, but entrepreneurial competencies have a significant impact. It is critical to understand how social cognitive factors influence entrepreneurial intention (Nwosu et al., 2022) therefore, SCT is most relevant for this study as it provides a comprehensive framework to investigate how entrepreneurial education influences students' cognition and subsequently entrepreneurial behaviour.

Overview of Entrepreneurship Education in HEIs

Entrepreneurship education aims to provide students with knowledge and skills on theoretical and conceptual frameworks that support entrepreneurship (Amalia & Korflesch, 2021). Parfirio, Carrilho, Jardim, and Wittberg (2022) proved that entrepreneurship education promotes students to pursue entrepreneurship as a career and provides them with the skills required; however, studies have proven that entrepreneurial education has been insufficient since HEIs produce graduates who are not equipped to engage in entrepreneurial activity (Zhou, Rashid, & Cheng, 2024). Higher education institutions hope to develop entrepreneurship awareness amongst students by implementing entrepreneurship programs and courses (Farid & Rahman, 2020). South African HEIs, for instance,

provide entrepreneurial programmes like ENACTUS and STEP, which support an action-based approach alongside academic theoretical courses (Otache, Akubo, & David, 2024). In 2018/19, the University of Venda began encouraging entrepreneurial activity, including projects, brief training, and event organising, to establish itself as a strong institution of higher learning focused on socio-economic development (Iwara & Kilonzo, 2022).

The Factors of Entrepreneurship Education that Contribute to Student Entrepreneurship Development

Entrepreneurship Knowledge and Skills: Entrepreneurship promotion aims to equip undergraduates with necessary skills to create something new, to solve problems and determine prospects; this means that entrepreneurship promotion can play an essential role in equipping university students with the skills to launch businesses upon graduation (Edokpolor, 2020). Furthermore, a degree in entrepreneurship can prepare students with various knowledge and skills, such as the capacity to spot opportunities, seize them by formulating new concepts and gathering the necessary funding, as well as launch and oversee a new business, while exercising critical and creative thought (Chimucheka, 2014).

Entrepreneurial Mindsets: Khalil, Hashim, Rababa, and Atallah (2024) assert that the higher education system is essential to the development of entrepreneurs, in that HEIs have the potential to mould entrepreneurial mindsets. Moreover, entrepreneurship promotion can help students adopt attitudes and mindsets that are not afraid of taking risks, failing, and competing (Chimucheka, 2014; Deng & Wang, 2023). This view is supported by Porfirio, Carrilho, Jardim, and Wittberg (2022) who argued that perceptions of students' potential for entrepreneurship include risk-taking and innovativeness; these can be modified by methodical and ongoing effort of entrepreneurship courses.

Entrepreneurship Intentions: Entrepreneurship intention is not inherited, but established through entrepreneurship education (Tshehla et al., 2020). An intention is referred to as an individual's desire and willingness to start a venture or to behave in an entrepreneurial manner (Phiri & Chasaya, 2023). Entrepreneurship education improves students' intention by establishing a business culture (Deng & Wang, 2023). As such, the goal of entrepreneurship education in universities is seen as a catalyst for encouraging relevant intentions, ultimately contributing to the development of future entrepreneurs (Chahal, Shoukat, & Ayoubi, 2024). Shah, Amjed, and Jaboo (2020) also pointed out that entrepreneurship education encourages students to establish their own enterprises at some point in their careers.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted at the University of Venda, which is a rural-based university located in Thohoyandou, in the Vhembe District of the Limpopo Province. Thohoyandou serves as the administrative centre of the Vhembe District and Thulamela Municipality. The University of Venda is a higher education institution that was established in 1982 to meet the apartheid-era educational demands of the people living in the Venda Bantustan.

Method

Participants

This study targeted University of Venda students, who are informal

entrepreneurs involved in programs and competitions, and students registered for the entrepreneurship module. Due to various entrepreneurial education programmes offered at the University of Venda and students being involved in diverse business activities on campus, the size of the population is not known.

This study utilised non-probability; a sampling process that selects people in a non-random manner, hence, not every person may be included. This study followed the convenience sampling method. A non-probabilistic sampling technique known as the "convenience method" is used when members of a target population satisfy specific practical requirements or criteria. The criteria could be things like - willingness to engage in the study, availability at a specific time, geographic proximity, and convenience of access (Obilor, 2023). This study collected data from 10 students, at which point, data saturation was achieved. A sample size of 10 is not uncommon in qualitative research; for instance, in their work, Shumba and Nkondo (2020) conducted 5 in-depth interviews.

Research Design and Approach

A research design is a plan, framework or strategy that a researcher employs to produce responses to research questions (Kumatongo & Muzata, 2021). Three theoretical frameworks, namely phenomenology, hermeneutics and ethnography, are the primary pillars of the qualitative research approach (Muzari, Shava, & Shonhiwa, 2022) this study employed a phenomenology design. A phenomenological study describes the common meaning of various people's lived experiences within a given topic or situation (Sarfo, Debrah, Gbordzoe, Affal, & Obeng, 2021). The researcher employed a qualitative research approach, which, according to Bhangu, Provost, and Caduff (2023), is a technique that aims to explore and comprehend the meaning that individuals or groups ascribe to social or human phenomenon. Rather than using numerical data, qualitative research typically employs verbal data / texts (Betto et al., 2020) its main aim is to understand the experiences that people have, according to Merriam and Tisdell (2016).

Research Paradigm

The study followed the constructive paradigm, which postulates that people build their own knowledge and comprehension of the world due to their ideas and experiences (Kamal, 2019). It was selected because, it seeks to comprehend the social environment of the people being studied and entails viewing that environment through the eyes of the individuals who inhabit it (Bogna, Raineri, & Dell, 2020).

Data Collection and Analysis

In this study, data was collected through semi-structured interviews. Semi-structured interviews feature open-ended questions and the use of interview guidelines to outline broad areas of interest and facilitate the process (Ruslin et al., 2022). Interviews are used to learn about an individual's subjective experiences, attitudes, and motives, rather than facts and conduct (Busetto, 2020).

The researchers conducted thematic content analysis on the collected data with Atlas.ti version 8.4. Thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis approach that identifies themes within a given dataset (Lester, Cho, & Lochmiller, 2020). Atlas. ti is a qualitative research software that is used for coding and analysing transcripts and creating network diagrams. The researcher used mainly coding and continuous comparison to analyse data. Coding is a data analysis technique that involves reading and interpreting raw

contextualised data to construct themes and the relationship between them. Open coding is the initial level of coding during which the researcher identifies themes, categorises them then assigns codes (Williams & Moser, 2019).

Trustworthiness Criteria

Reliability: Reliability in qualitative research pertains to the degree of consistency exhibited by data-gathering instruments. According to this principle, research in qualitative analysis should be documented in a way that allows other researchers to examine the data and reach similar results (Nassaji, 2020). The research used an audit trail for monitoring and keeping raw data such as Interview documents and audio recordings to reduce systematic bias and verify the honesty of participants' responses.

Validity Conclusion

Validity is defined as the degree to which a study measures the concepts it claims to measure. In other words, a study is considered valid if it accurately represents the target structures or variables being studied (William, 2024). The researcher employed an audit trail for readers to validate data, which involves monitoring and keeping all the records of research activities and field collected raw data such as interview documents and audio recordings, for other interested researchers and stakeholders.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers informed the respondents about the nature and goal of the study before beginning data collection; therefore, the participants' participation was based on their informed consent. The researchers also informed the participants that their participation was voluntary, which meant they may withdraw from the study at any time, without any penalty. Participants were assigned pseudonyms to guarantee that their contributions are anonymous.

Results

This section gives an interpretation of the study findings derived from the responses received; the primary method of data gathering was a semi-structured, face-to-face interview. The findings were obtained in relation to the research goals stated in the background and introduction to the study.

Demographics

This section presents the demographics of participants as shown in Table 1. The researcher investigated the role of entrepreneurship education on student entrepreneurship development. The student entrepreneurs under investigation are University of Venda students from different degree programs but are also involved in entrepreneurship. The student entrepreneurs are participating in ENACTUS and STEP entrepreneurship programs.

Table 1
Demographics of Participants

Participant	Education and training	Entrepreneurship program	Years of operation
1	BCom in Business Management	Entrepreneurship module, Enactus, STEP	5
2	Bachelor of Agriculture	STEP	4
3	Bachelor of Education	STEP	
4	Honours in Business Management	Entrepreneurship module	3
5	BCom in Business Management	Entrepreneurship module	3
6	Master's in Psychology	STEP	10
7	Honours in Business Management	Entrepreneurship module, Enactus	4
8	BCom Tourism	Enactus	5
9	BA in Public Relations	STEP	2
10	BSc in Environmental Science	STEP	3

Conceptualisation of the Factors of EE that Contribute to Student Entrepreneurship Development

This section presents the factors of entrepreneurship education that contribute to student entrepreneurship development. During data analysis, seven themes were extracted from the data and coded. The codes were: access to financial resources; entrepreneurial centre; entrepreneurial knowledge and skills; entrepreneurial mindset; mentorship and coaching; networking opportunities; and practical experience.

Access to Financial Resources

The results in this study have shown that access to financial resources is one of the factors of entrepreneurship education that influences student entrepreneurship development. This is evidenced by the views of Participants 1, 2, 3, 6 and 9 as shown in the excerpts below:

"In ENACTUS programme they host competition whereby students present their business ideas and the student with the best idea gets a start-up capital of a certain amount." Participant 1

"I also received financial support from NYDA I received a grant of R5000 after attending their training, which helped me to start my farming business." Participant 2

"When you participate in STEP workshop, at the end of the workshop you are given R2000 as a start-up capital for your business idea, so I've gained uhm finance if I can put it like that, funds or capital to start-up my business." Participant 3

"It assists most of the young people to grow. Uhm, more especially at the program that I partake in because they also make sure that they give you a start-up capital," Participant 6

"Access to startup funding." Participant 9

From the above excerpts, the respondents disclosed that they receive financial resources from the entrepreneurship programs that

they participate in. They indicated that they received start-up capital from ENACTUS, STEP, as well as NYDA upon completion of the training. The participants indicated that the start-up capital that they received from these entrepreneurship education programs helped them to implement their business ideas. This proves that access to financial resources influences student entrepreneurship development.

Entrepreneurship Centre

The results indicate that the existence of an entrepreneurship centre is one of the notable factors that contribute to student entrepreneurship development. This is revealed by the perceptions of Participants 1 and 2 from the quotations below:

“Univen has established an entrepreneurship centre where they conduct entrepreneurial workshops and events.” Participant 1

“The University of Venda foster entrepreneurship culture on campus by hosting entrepreneurship competitions, events and they have also developed an entrepreneurship centre.” Participant 2

The above extracts revealed that the University of Venda has established an entrepreneurial centre aimed at fostering entrepreneurial culture among students, through hosting entrepreneurship events, workshops and competitions. The entrepreneurial centre actively engages students and encourages their participation in entrepreneurship education. This initiative plays a crucial role in shaping students' interest in entrepreneurial activities.

Entrepreneurial mindset

Entrepreneurial mindset is another factor of entrepreneurship education that contributes to student entrepreneurship development. This is revealed by Participants 1, 2, 4 and 5 in the following quotations:

“Entrepreneurship education shifted my mindset from wanting to work for someone to wanting to be my own boss and create employment for other people. I started to see entrepreneurship as the way to success.” Participant 1

“Entrepreneurship education has helped me develop an entrepreneurial mindset, which has helped me to approach challenges with creativity, perseverance and adaptability.” Participant 2

“Entrepreneurship education programmes play a vital role by fostering a mindset that embraces innovation, risk-taking and problem-solving.” Participant 4

“According to my point of view, I think it develops entrepreneurial mindset in such a way that the knowledge that is imparted to entrepreneurship education students lead to many of them being entrepreneurs.” Participant 5

From the quotations above, the students expressed that entrepreneurship education played a significant role in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. They further indicated that they started to perceive entrepreneurship as a viable career option through their participation in entrepreneurship education. These results show that students have gained mindset that can tolerate risks, that navigate challenges with creativity and resilience and enables them to bounce back from setbacks. This provides clear evidence that entrepreneurship education contributes to the development of student entrepreneurship by instilling in students an entrepreneurial mindset.

Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Skills

The findings show that entrepreneurial knowledge and skills is identified as another factor that influences student entrepreneurship development. This is showed by the responses of participants 8, 9, and 10 in the following extracts.

“You see that when someone now is taught about entrepreneurship, there's a concept for positive impact creation, for example, right? There's an aspect for opportunity identification, there's now an aspect of managing finances, there's an aspect of marketing, there's an aspect of registering the business. So, through those entrepreneurship education programmes you see that people they get now acquitted with those things that are acquired within the entrepreneurship arena.” Participant 8

“Entrepreneurship education programs have helped refine my start-up ideas by teaching me how to develop business plans, conduct market research, and pitch to investors.” Participant 9

“I think the most beneficial one it has to be financial literacy, marketing strategies, and also communication skills.” Participant 10

The above extracts confirm that entrepreneurship programs equip students with essential entrepreneurial knowledge and skills. The students reported that they acquired skills such as business planning, marketing research, financial management, creativity, risk-taking, innovation, and problem-solving. These skills played an essential role in shaping their entrepreneurial mindsets. These are entrepreneurial skills that they developed through entrepreneurship education, hence, are crucial in successfully implementing and maintaining a business.

Mentorship and Coaching

The study findings illustrated that mentorship and coaching were noted as other factors of entrepreneurship education that influence student entrepreneurship development. This is demonstrated by the views of Participants 1, 2, 3 and 9 as shown in the quotes underneath:

“In the STEP programme we attend workshops and events where successful entrepreneurs share their success stories and teach us how to navigate the entrepreneurship journey and tackle challenges of starting and managing a business.” Participant 1

“Mentorship by facilitators of the program.” Participant 2

“STEP provides us with mentorship, so when we attend this, uhm programmes we are provided with entrepreneurship facilitators who help us to navigate through, uh, how to start a business, how to go on about it, and also we are offered mentors to mentor us throughout the journey.” Participant 3

“The most beneficial aspects of EE include mentorship opportunities.” Participant 9

From the above extracts, the students indicated that they receive valuable mentorship and coaching from entrepreneurship facilitators involved in the programs. These facilitators provide guidance on how to implement a successful business and navigate the challenges that one may come across when implementing and running a business. They also revealed that the entrepreneurial programs host events and workshops where successful entrepreneurs are invited to share their success stories. These engagements motivate students, especially those who may be hesitant to pursue entrepreneurship due to fear of failure. The

mentorship programme has had a huge influence in developing entrepreneurial mindset because students often perceive these mentors and facilitators as role models and imitate their behaviour, subsequently leading them to take the initiative to start their businesses.

Networking Opportunities

The results of this study elucidated that networking opportunities are perceived as other aspects that contribute to student entrepreneurship development. This is evidenced by the views of Participants 1, 2, 3 and 9 as illustrated in the quotations below:

“The most important aspect is networking opportunities with successful entrepreneurs.” Participant 1

“Networking opportunities with successful entrepreneurs.” Participant 2

“It provides networking because when one attends this kind of workshops you get to meet, uh successful entrepreneurs who have knowledge about the ins and outs of entrepreneurship and how to start a business, how to navigate through the business journey.” Participant 3

“Networking with industry experts.” Participant 9

From the above extracts, the respondents disclosed that partaking in entrepreneurship program offered them an opportunity to connect with experienced entrepreneurs. Networking with industry experts, therefore, enabled them to gain comprehensive understanding of how to navigate the entrepreneurial journey. This highlights the

significant role networking plays in supporting student entrepreneurship development.

Practical Experience

The research findings revealed that practical experience is another factor that contributes to student entrepreneurship development. This is evidenced by the opinions of Participants 4, 8 and 9 in the extracts below:

“The most beneficial aspects have been the hands-on approach to learning, exposure, and case studies.” Participant 4

“The one that I can give relevance to was Enactus, right? Because with Enactus, we could go to communities and be able to assist the entrepreneurs there with their business planning, marketing, you know, operation planning, and financial planning.” Participant 8

“Experiential learning.” Participant 9

From the quotes above, the students specified that after the training, they go and practice what they have been taught. They unveiled that in the Enactus program, they practice their taught skills by going to the nearby communities and helping entrepreneurs with business planning, financial planning, marketing, as well as operational planning. Through assisting entrepreneurs in the communities, they get exposed to the real-world experience; they apply their theoretical knowledge into real-world situations. This is evidence that the entrepreneurial programs provide students with practical experience.

Summary of the factors of EE that contribute to student entrepreneurship development is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1
Factors of EE that Contribute to Student Entrepreneurship Development

Note. Source: Factors of entrepreneurship education using Atlas.ti

Discussion

This section provides a discussion of the results of the analysed data. The current study revealed that entrepreneurship education provides students with financial resources to successfully establish and maintain their ventures. The students specified that they receive financial assistance from STEP, ENACTUS and NYDA. This result concurs with the study of Rukmana et al. (2023) which stated that

entrepreneurship education provides student entrepreneurs with access to early-stage funding, venture capital networks, and support in securing grants and loans, which are considered crucial for firms' growth and viability. Similar findings were obtained from the study conducted by Awonuga et al. (2024) who mentioned that entrepreneurship education provides students with access to funding through incubation.

The observation that the University of Venda has established

an entrepreneurial centre to foster entrepreneurial culture among students, through hosting entrepreneurial events, workshops and training, was also made in the study of Iwara (2023) who indicated that the University of Venda concentrates on imparting entrepreneurial knowledge and skills through establishing an entrepreneurship training centre. Similar contents were found in the study of Thaba-Nkadimene, Masebe, and Mashitola (2024) which states that the establishment of entrepreneurship and innovation hubs enables hands-on entrepreneurship experiences.

The respondents in this study revealed that entrepreneurship education has played a crucial role in shaping their entrepreneurial mindsets. The same sentiment was echoed in the research done by Boahemaah, Xin, Dobge, and Pomegbe (2020) who assert that entrepreneurship education helps individuals to cultivate a mindset which fosters a good attitude, motivation and capacity, in relation to entrepreneurship. These sentiments were also made in the study of Cheteni and Lose (2023) who concluded that entrepreneurship modules open up students' mindset and their perceptions about entrepreneurship. The outcomes in the study of Rankhumise and Letsoalo (2023) however, suggest that entrepreneurship education exerted a negligible influence on cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset among students enrolled in the programs, which contradicts the findings of this study.

The current study states that entrepreneurship education equips students with the necessary knowledge and skills needed to embark on entrepreneurship. This finding corroborates those of Rankhumise and Letsoalo (2023) who maintain that entrepreneurship education equips students with essential knowledge, skills and competencies necessary to establish and manage a business. Obaje (2024) however, concluded that the current approach to entrepreneurship education does not provide students with the necessary skills to succeed as entrepreneurs, which contradicts with the findings of the current study. This non-support is echoed by the study of Ellikkal and Rajamohan (2023) that the entrepreneurship education system is inadequately developed and lacks the capacity to convey entrepreneurial information, skills and abilities, as well as to cultivate entrepreneurial interest among students.

The participants reported that they receive mentorship and coaching from facilitators of entrepreneurship education programs who do guide them through the process of starting a new business. This study's findings are in line with those in the study of Awonuga et al. (2024) who maintain that mentorship provides significant insights, expertise and assistance for new entrepreneurs.

The findings revealed that students get an opportunity to network with their peers, investors, and industry experts through entrepreneurship education programmes. The assertion is confirmed by Karambakuwa (2021) that entrepreneurship education enables networking with like-minded individuals to exchange ideas and opportunities. Similarly, Rakmana et al. (2023) report that entrepreneurship education programs can establish a strong network through networking events and workshops to facilitate collaboration and information-sharing among aspiring and experienced entrepreneurs, investors and industry professionals.

The current study acknowledged practical experience as another factor of entrepreneurship education that influences students' entrepreneurial intentions. A study by Saleh et al. (2020) contradicts the findings of the current study by stipulating that the focus of most entrepreneurship education is imparting theoretical knowledge

rather than practice.

Conclusion

This study identified the factors as - access to financial resources; entrepreneurship centre; entrepreneurial mindset; entrepreneurial knowledge and skills; mentorship and coaching; networking opportunities; and practical experience. In terms of access to financial resources, the findings indicated that students receive a startup capital from the entrepreneurship programs to implement their ideas. Regarding entrepreneurship centre, the results indicated that the University of Venda has established an entrepreneurship centre, where they offer training to students. Pertaining to an entrepreneurial mindset, the results disclosed that entrepreneurship education plays a significant role in shaping students' mindset since, it equips students with entrepreneurial knowledge and skills.

In addition, with reference to mentorship and coaching, the results showed that students access mentorship and coaching from facilitators of entrepreneurship programme, who guide them throughout the entrepreneurship development journey. Regarding networking opportunities, the findings revealed that students gain networking opportunities with their peers and experienced entrepreneurs. On the issue of practical experience, the participants maintained that they gain practical experience through engaging with entrepreneurs in the community who help them with business planning, financial management, and marketing research.

Recommendations

Entrepreneurship education should be compulsory in all disciplines, across all faculties, in HEIs. The government should allocate adequate funding and resources to support entrepreneurship programs in universities. Entrepreneurship lecturers should be regularly trained and encouraged in research to stay updated with the recent entrepreneurship trends.

Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted at the University of Venda; this means the results may not be applicable to other universities; however, certain inferences can be drawn, albeit with caution. This study was also a qualitative one, hence, a small sample size was utilised.

Future Research

The researcher suggests that a comparable study be undertaken at another university to determine any similarities or variations in the findings. A mixed-method research approach is also recommended to gain a thorough understanding of the subject matter.

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